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MARKETING PROBLEMS IN THE INTERNATIONAL INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE MARKET AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN SOLVING THEM

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Abstract: This article analyzes the market position of the textile industry by country, the promotion of the textile sector across different countries, and the support provided to the textile industry in Asian countries. In addition, it examines the study and application of positive foreign experience to assist the textile industry of Uzbekistan in securing its position in the global market.

Key words: market, foreign experience, textiles, export, innovation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mamlakatlar kesimida to'qimachilik sanoatining bozordagi o'rni, turli mamlakatlarda to'qimachilik sanoatini rivojlantirish va ilgari surish masalalari, shuningdek Osiyo mamlakatlarida ushbu tarmoqni qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, O'zbekiston to'qimachilik sanoatining jahon bozorida munosib o'rin egallashiga ko'maklashish maqsadida xorijiy mamlakatlarning ijobiy tajribasini o'rganish va amaliyotga joriy etish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: bozor, xorijiy tajriba, to'qimachilik, eksport, innovatsiya.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется рыночное положение текстильной промышленности в разрезе стран, вопросы продвижения текстильной отрасли в различных государствах, а также меры поддержки текстильной промышленности в странах Азии. Кроме того, рассматриваются вопросы изучения и применения положительного зарубежного опыта с целью содействия занятию текстильной промышленностью Узбекистана достойного места на мировом рынке.

Ключевые слова: рынок, зарубежный опыт, текстиль, экспорт, инновации.

INTRODUCTION

The textile industry represents a dynamically developing global market, in which the main competitors are China, the European Union, the United States, and India. China is the world's leading producer and exporter of textiles and apparel. The United States is the largest producer and exporter of raw cotton and, at the same time, one of the largest importers of textiles and clothing. The textile industry of the European Union includes such countries as Germany, Spain, France, Italy, and Portugal, which together account for more than one-fifth of the global textile industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The analysis of the existing literature indicates the importance of improving modern market principles, enhancing brand promotion methods, and adopting a flexible approach to meeting consumer needs in order to strengthen national competitiveness. In his textbook on market strategies, R. Ibragimov defines marketing

strategy as follows: "Marketing strategy is understood as the application of a model of enterprise behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its sustainable success."

Many economists and scholars have contributed to the development and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such well-known researchers as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Baer.

At the same time, marketing research conducted in our country, while taking into account national characteristics, has also been enriched by the significant contributions of local scholars to the development of marketing theory. These include R. Ibragimov, Yo. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva, and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. In addition, data collection and analysis were carried out using large-scale monitoring methods based on information obtained from social media platforms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to a report published by Global Market Insights, the global smart textile market was valued at USD 2.147 billion in 2021, and this figure is expected to increase to USD 16.4 billion by 2030. Based on other sources, the size of this market is estimated at USD 1.94 trillion in 2024 and is forecast to reach USD 4.91 trillion by 2037.

As shown in Figure 1, cotton products account for the largest share of the textile market (40%), while, in terms of regions, the Asia-Pacific countries represent one of the main segments of the manufacturing market, with a share of 52%.

In 2024, China remains the world's largest producer and exporter of textiles. It accounts for more than 30% of the global market and exports its products to more than 200 countries and regions.

According to reports of the World Trade Organization (WTO), the leading countries in the production and export of textile products include India, which specializes in the production of cotton, woolen fabrics, and silk; the Netherlands, where textile manufacturers широко apply digital printing and innovative dyeing methods; the United Kingdom, which exports wool, silk, cotton, synthetic materials, and special fabrics for various industries; Spain, whose cotton, wool, linen, silk, and synthetic fabrics are supplied to global markets; Pakistan, which has significant cotton reserves and is therefore one of the leading producers of cotton-based materials; and Sri Lanka, which specializes in the production and export of high-quality textile products, including cotton, silk, synthetic, linen, and woolen fabrics.

At the same time, due to strong competition in the global market for textiles, garments, and knitwear, the leading positions among exporting countries are subject to continuous change. An analysis of the factors ensuring the market positions of the textile industry in different countries shows that large-scale measures to stimulate the development of this sector are being implemented worldwide. This policy is particularly evident in the Asian region. The analysis indicates that support for the textile industry in Asian countries is primarily focused on the development of small and medium-sized enterprises, especially microenterprises. In order for the textile industry of Uzbekistan to secure a stable and competitive position in the global market, it is advisable to study and apply the positive experience of foreign countries. In this regard, the state policies aimed at supporting the textile industry in several countries have been examined.

People's Republic of China

The share of the garment and textile industry in China's total GDP exceeds 11%. Tax revenues from the textile and garment sector enable the country to generate up to 15–20% of the state budget. The textile and garment industry occupies the largest share among light industry subsectors, contributing approximately every fifth yuan to the national budget. Currently, about 400,000 different clothing brands are produced in China, of which nearly 50% are foreign brands.

China's light industry policy includes the following key measures:

- the establishment of a special state fund to support small and medium-sized enterprises;
- the introduction of preferential tax regimes;
- the provision of financial and credit support;
- ensuring access for small businesses to government procurement;
- the implementation of other incentive measures.

With regard to specific measures in the textile industry, the following main areas of support can be highlighted:

1. the establishment of a special state fund to support small and medium-sized enterprises;
2. ensuring the participation of small businesses in government procurement, with at least 30% of the annual public procurement budget allocated to SMEs;
3. the development of mechanisms to support both small and medium-sized enterprises and the institutions that guarantee the repayment of loans granted to them;
4. export support, including a gradual increase in tax refund rates for many types of exported light industry products (garments, textiles, etc.);
5. the allocation of funds for the modernization of production technologies;
6. measures to encourage enterprises to relocate production capacities from southeastern China to central and western regions;
7. the expansion of urban and rural consumption and the improvement of the efficiency of supplying light industry products to the domestic market;
8. the enhancement of foreign trade services and the maintenance of the share of light industry products in export markets.

India

India is the only country in the world that produces four types of silk. It ranks second globally after China, with silk production amounting to 34.9 thousand tons. The textile and garment industry accounts for 2.3% of the country's GDP, 13% of industrial output, and 12% of total exports. The Indian textile and garment market is expected to grow at an average annual rate of 10% and reach USD 350 billion by 2030, while the sector's share in GDP is projected to increase to 5%. This growth trend is observed across various segments of the industry; in particular, the technical textiles market for the automotive sector is expected to expand from USD 2.4 billion in 2020 to USD 3.7 billion by 2027.

According to the India Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF), India is currently the world's third-largest exporter of textiles and apparel and the fifth-largest market for technical textiles. In 2024, exports amounted to USD 36 billion, accounting for about 12% of the country's total export revenues.

Government-supported programs focus on promoting the localization of textile production and exports, including initiatives such as Make in India and Aatmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan. The Skill India program provides subsidies to educational institutions for the development of specialized training programs. In addition, a dedicated program to support the technical textile industry, the National Technical Textile Mission, has been introduced.

To promote textile exports, nine Export Promotion Councils have been established in India. Each council focuses on a specific product category and monitors market opportunities for Indian goods. Several mechanisms and funds have been created to provide state support to textile enterprises, including:

- the Technology Upgradation Fund Scheme (TUFS), which provides compensation and subsidies to manufacturers;
- the Scheme for Integrated Textile Parks (SITP), aimed at establishing modern textile parks;
- the Mega Cluster Development Scheme, designed to support weavers and artisans in home-based industries;
- the Integrated Skills Development Scheme (ISDS), which focuses on upgrading the skills of workers in the textile sector.

Currently, the government is actively promoting the establishment of specialized industrial zones by offering tax incentives and subsidies to enterprises operating in these regions. For example, in August 2023, the creation of seven specialized industrial zones under the PM Integrated Textile and Garment Park (PM MITRA) initiative was approved. According to IBEF, these parks are expected to be equipped with world-class infrastructure by 2027–2028, with total investments amounting to USD 535 million.

Bangladesh

The textile industry is one of the key sectors of the Bangladeshi economy, with approximately 3,500 garment factories operating in the country. Bangladesh plays a significant role in the global textile and garment trade and represents an important link in the international textile supply chain. The textile and garment industry forms the backbone of the national economy and makes a substantial contribution to global markets.

Bangladesh is widely known for manufacturing apparel for major international brands, including Adidas, Levi's, Calvin Klein, Zara, and H&M. The export of ready-made garments constitutes the core of the country's foreign trade. By the end of December 2024, the Bangladeshi garment industry earned USD 50 billion in export revenues, which represents an increase of 8.3% compared to the previous year. The dominance of ready-made

garments in exports and the strong reliance of global brands on Bangladeshi factories highlight the country's strategic importance in international production chains.

The textile industry is of particular importance to the Bangladeshi economy for several reasons. First, exports of textiles and garments serve as a major source of foreign exchange earnings. According to the Export Promotion Bureau (EPB), export revenues from the garment industry reached USD 50 billion by the end of December 2024, reflecting an annual growth of 8.3%. Second, the availability of relatively low-cost labor, supported by high population density, contributes to competitive production costs. Third, the sector is characterized by the development of enterprises specializing in various product categories, including knitted fabrics, woven fabrics, and yarns. Fourth, the country has accumulated considerable industrial experience since the mid-1970s, and in recent years, specialization in the textile sector has become an important component of national development strategy. Finally, the garment industry has created significant employment opportunities for women, particularly in rural areas, thereby enhancing social inclusion.

Overall, the garment industry accounts for more than 80% of Bangladesh's total export earnings and contributes approximately 11% of the country's GDP. The value of exports increased from about USD 5 billion in 2001 to nearly USD 40 billion in 2023, reflecting the устойчивое and dynamic development of the sector.

Pakistan

Pakistan is one of the largest textile-producing countries and exports textile products worth approximately USD 31 billion annually, mainly to European and U.S. markets. The country's textile industry is well developed, integrated into the global value chain, and supplies products to well-known international brands. In addition, Pakistan benefits from the GSP+ system, which further supports its export potential. The textile and garment sector represents the largest segment of the country's light industry and is among the most significant in the world.

The textile industry accounts for about 8.5% of Pakistan's GDP, while textile exports constitute a substantial share of the country's total exports. Moreover, the sector employs approximately one-third of the industrial workforce, highlighting its strategic importance for economic development and social stability.

Pakistan is one of the leading textile producers in Asia due to several key factors. First, the country has a strong domestic raw material base: most of the inputs used in the textile industry, including cotton fiber, wool, and finished fabrics, are produced locally, which helps to reduce production costs and enhance international competitiveness. Second, Pakistan possesses significant production capacity, including cotton ginning facilities, spinning mills, and both large and small textile and garment factories. Third, the industry is characterized by a wide range of products: Pakistani textile enterprises export cotton, wool, linen, silk, and synthetic fabrics in various colors, textures, and patterns. Finally, the country has accumulated specialized knowledge and expertise, particularly in the production of functional textiles, including fabrics containing silver fibers.

Vietnam

More than 7,000 enterprises operate in Vietnam's textile and garment industry, employing over 3 million people. More than 80% of total output is exported. In 2023, clothing exports amounted to approximately USD 44 billion, representing an increase of 11.26% compared to the previous year. At the same time, Vietnam's textile industry is closely linked to external market conditions, and in 2024 a noticeable decline in exports was observed.

In order to support the textile industry and stabilize export performance, the government has implemented a set of comprehensive measures. These include creating material and financial conditions for the introduction of new, highly productive technologies in textile enterprises, reducing internal production costs, improving the business environment for exporters, and attracting foreign investment into the sector. Taken together, these measures are aimed at strengthening the long-term competitiveness and sustainability of the industry.

European Union States

State support for industry in the European Union countries is mainly horizontal in nature and includes both economic and regulatory measures, rather than being directed exclusively at the light industry sector. At the macroeconomic level, such support includes the improvement of tax policy (including tax incentives and simplification procedures), the enhancement of monetary policy (through preferential credit conditions), the optimization of customs policy (including incentives for foreign investment in light industry enterprises), export support mechanisms (such as export credits and state guarantees), as well as the development of business infrastructure and the strengthening of cooperation within the European Union.

At the microeconomic level, priority is given to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises. This includes policies aimed at stimulating competition, reducing administrative barriers, improving access to financial resources, providing preferences for the export of goods and capital, and offering assistance in accessing foreign markets.

Spain

Considering Spain as a country with a well-developed textile and clothing industry, the turnover of enterprises in this sector in 2024 amounted to approximately EUR 49–50 billion, while direct value added reached about EUR 9.2–9.5 billion. The sustainable development of the Spanish textile industry is based on several key factors. One of these is the use of sustainable raw materials, including the expansion of environmentally friendly and recycled inputs in production, such as recycled cotton, raw materials derived from recycled plastic waste, as well as silk and wool produced in accordance with sustainability standards.

Another important factor is the focus on maximizing production efficiency. In the context of implementing ISO 14001 environmental management systems at textile enterprises, scientific and technological innovations are being introduced to reduce energy consumption, minimize waste, and decrease the use of water and other natural resources.

Currently, the main trends in the Spanish textile industry include the introduction of circular economy principles, the reduction of carbon emissions, the optimization of cost management and product delivery processes, and the promotion of technological development.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The textile, garment, and knitwear industry occupies one of the leading positions in the national economy. Its share in the manufacturing sector is approximately 17%, and it is regarded as one of the industries with high export potential. In addition, the textile, garment, and knitwear industry makes a substantial contribution to addressing key development objectives, such as the deep processing of local agricultural raw materials and the creation of employment opportunities for the population.

The textile, garment, and knitwear industry is characterized by a number of specific features and therefore requires systematic state support to ensure sustainable competitiveness in the global market. Since 2019, a favorable environment for investment in the sector has been formed through the provision of incentives to manufacturers and the development of international logistics systems.

The uniqueness of products in the textile, garment, and knitwear industry, as well as the specific characteristics of enterprises operating in this sector, have a significant influence on the content and structural elements of marketing activities.

The study shows that the classification of textile, sewing, and knitting enterprises can be carried out according to the following criteria: type of enterprise, type of market, and market position. In particular, all enterprises can be grouped into three major categories: enterprises producing yarn and thread (IK), textile products (T), and finished sewing and knitting products (TT). By market orientation, enterprises may focus on the consumer market, the business-to-business market, or foreign markets. In terms of market position, enterprises can be classified as having high, medium, or low positions.

For Uzbekistan, studying the experience of Asian countries that are leaders in the textile industry and analyzing the factors behind their development, especially in terms of accelerating marketing activities in international markets, is of significant scientific and practical importance. Foreign experience demonstrates that the combination of an active enterprise-level marketing system and consistent state support for the industry serves as a key guarantee for the formation of a favorable marketing environment and the effective implementation of marketing activities.

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